

Least Cost electrification options for Suriname using OnSSET

Amrita Raghoebarsing, Anton de Kom University of Suriname, Suriname

February 1, 2024

■

Keywords: Least Cost electrification option, Energy planning, OnSSET, Suriname, LCOE

Acknowledgement

This report was produced during the EMP-LAC 24 capacity building event organized by the Climate Compatible Growth Programme (CCG). The OnSSET training was provided by dr. Andreas Sahlberg. The event received funding from CCG, the World Bank Group (WBG), and the 2050 Pathways Platform.

Executive Summary

In order to have 100% electrification rate for Suriname till 2030, there are several options as the least cost electrification option for different settlements in Suriname like the existing grid, stand alone PV systems, mini grid hydro systems, mini grid wind hybrid systems, mini-grid PV hybrid systems and grid extension. Until 2023, nearly 117593 new connections need to be made of which 50% can be done with the existing grid or grid extension for the rural areas. While the urban areas can be electrified by with stand alone PV systems, mini grid PV systems, mini grid hydro systems or mini grid wind hybrid. About 52 - 61MW new capacity and \$290 - \$360 million new investment will be required to reach the electrification rate at 100% till 2030. In the interior, the investment must be mainly done in stand alone PV systems (30,000 – 40,000 new connections) and mini grid hydro systems (16,000 - 20,000 new connections). In the regions with existing grid the LCOE varies between \$0.087 to \$0.12 per kWh. While in the interior, most of the villages where stand-alone PV system can be installed the LCOE can range from \$0.30 to \$0.40 per kWh for the BAU while it can be cheaper (\$0.12 to \$0.20/kWh) if the CAPEX of PV is 0.5 times less. But if the demand goes up then the LCOE can be more than \$0.40 per kWh. At some of the settlements can be electrified with mini grid PV but the LCOE will be more than \$1/kWh. Along the Suriname river, mini grid hydro is an option with an LCOE of \$0.12 – \$0.30 per kWh.

1. Introduction

The Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET) is an open source, spatial electrification tool estimating, analysing and visualizing the most cost effective electrification option (grid, mini grid & stand-alone) for the achievement of electricity access goals. The tool is focused on the assessment and deployment of conventional and renewable energy technologies aiming at ensuring access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all (SDG 7). OnSSET, is a tool, designed to fill the gap between the analytical toolbox available to the energy research community and energy planners throughout the world (Anon., 2024).

In this report, the OnSSET tool is used to determine least-cost electrification options for Suriname. Suriname is the smallest country in South America by both population and territory, with around 623,236 (2023) inhabitants in an area of approximately 163,820 km². With nearly 87% of the people living along the coastal plain. Currently the capital, Paramaribo, and the surrounding districts are connected to the national grid (Fig. 1). There are also some small central grids e.g. in district Nickerie and Marowijne. But as it can be seen in figure 1 (in green), there is no national grid in the interior (district Sipaliwini). Currently, the electrification rate is 98.82 % in Suriname.

Figure 1 The regions in Suriname with the existing grid (HV lines (in red) and MV lines (dark purple)).

■

The analysis was done for the entire country with a start year of 2020 and an end year of 2030. The purpose of this study is to determine the least cost electrification option in urban – and rural areas of Suriname in order to get 100% electrification rate by 2030. For this, different electricity generation systems will be compared using the levelized cost of energy (LCOE). This study has been done only for the residential sector of Suriname.

2. Methodology

Modeling Approach

OnSSET has been used for the modelling of least-cost electrification option in Suriname. This tool requires GIS data and non-GIS data as input. There are 2 different types of codes which must be run to get the results. Firstly, the GIS data needs to be extracted to each population cluster and saved in a CSV-format using the first python code in order to use for analysis in OnSSET. This CSV file can be used as the input file for the OnSSET python script. Sometimes the GIS data needs to be transformed in QGIS in order to get the appropriate format which can be used as input data in python. Secondly, the OnSSET python script must be run in order to get the results for the least-cost technology. For this, non-GIS data of the country is required. All these processes are given in the flowchart (Fig. 2) and all the data which were required and gathered for this study are given in the tables below.

Figure 2 Flowchart of Modelling Approach

Data sources

Table 1 and 2 give an overview of the dataset which is used for this study.

Table 1 GIS Datasets

Dataset		Source	Link	Info
Population clusters	2023			Created from WorldPop raster data: https://wopr.worldpop.org/
Land cover		GLC2000	https://www.diva-gis.org/gdata	
Night-time lights	2022	VIIRS	https://eogdata.mines.edu/products/vnl/#annual_v	Version 2.2, average masked
Substations		NV EBS		Shape file of utility company Suriname
Administrative boundaries		Gonini	https://www.gonini.org/	
GHI		Global Solar Atlas	https://globalsolaratlas.info/map	Annual GHI
WindSpeed		Global Wind Atlas	https://globalwindatlas.info/en	Wind speed at 50m
Roads		OpenStreetMap		Primary, secondary and tertiary roads collected using the QuickOSM plugin
Elevation		CGIAR-SRTM	https://www.diva-gis.org/gdata	SRTM30 dataset. CGIAR-SRTM data aggregated to 30 seconds
HV (existing)		OpenStreetMap	Retrieved from QuickOSM plugin, overpass api	
MV (existing)		Gridfinder	https://gridfinder.rdrn.me/	Clipped within 50 km of HV lines
Travel time	2015	Malaria Atlas Project	https://data.malariaatlas.org/maps	Global Travel Time to Cities

Table 2 Non GIS dataset

Dataset	Value	Source	Link
National electricity access rate	98.8%		https://trackingsdg7.esmap.org/country/suriname
Population data	623,236 (2023) 607,065 (2020)	World bank	
Population ratio	Urban pop ratio: 0.82 Rural pop ratio: 0.18		https://www.macrotrends.net/countries/SUR/suriname/urban-population#:~:text=Suriname%20urban%20population%20for%202022,a%201.16%25%20increase%20from%202018.
Household size	3.9 (Urban and rural)		https://globaldatalab.org/areadata/table/hhsize/SUR/?levels=1+4&interpolation=0&extrapolation=0
Technology specs & costs		NV EBS reports and IDB reports	

The non-GIS values used for the simulation are given in detail in appendix 1.

Scenarios or sensitivity analysis

For this study, three scenarios have been investigated. These scenarios are as followed:

Scenario 1: Business as usual (BAU)

The first scenario is the business as usual scenario. The cost and the demand have been the same as the actual situation currently in Suriname.

Scenario 2: Lower CAPEX for PV

This scenario is the same compared to BAU, only the CAPEX of PV has been 0.5 times lower compared to BAU.

Scenario 3: Higher demand for the rural area

This scenario is the same compared to BAU, only the demand of the rural areas has been set 2 times higher compared to BAU.

The details of the scenarios and the values that were varied for the simulation are given in the next table.

Table 3 Scenarios and variables

Scenario	Name	Demand	CAPEX PV
1	BAU	Rural demand: 1,200 kWh/household/year Urban demand: 9,600 kWh/household/year	<p># PV and Wind hybrid mini-grid costs</p> <p>pv_cost = 1600 # PV panel costs including BoS (PV inverter, charge controller) (USD/kW)</p> <p>battery_cost = 1000 # battery capital cost, USD/kWh of storage capacity</p> <p>inverter_cost = 230 # Battery inverter, USD/kW</p> <p>diesel_gen_cost = 378 # diesel generator capital cost, USD/kW rated power</p> <p>wind_cost = 2800</p> <p>sa_pv_capital_cost_1 = 9620 ### Stand-alone PV capital cost (USD/kW) for household systems under 20 W</p> <p>sa_pv_capital_cost_2 = 8780 ### Stand-alone PV capital cost (USD/kW) for household systems between 21-50 W</p> <p>sa_pv_capital_cost_3 = 6380 ### Stand-alone PV capital cost (USD/kW) for household systems between 51-100 W</p> <p>sa_pv_capital_cost_4 = 4470 ### Stand-alone PV capital cost (USD/kW) for household systems between 101-1000 W</p>
2	Lower CAPEX for PV	Rural demand: 1,200 kWh/household/year Urban demand: 9,600 kWh/household/year	<p># PV and Wind hybrid mini-grid costs</p> <p>pv_cost = 800 # PV panel costs including BoS (PV inverter, charge controller) (USD/kW)</p> <p>battery_cost = 500 # battery capital cost, USD/kWh of storage capacity</p> <p>inverter_cost = 115 # Battery inverter, USD/kW</p> <p>diesel_gen_cost = 378 # diesel generator capital cost, USD/kW rated power</p> <p>wind_cost = 2800</p>

			<p>sa_pv_capital_cost_1 = 9620/2 ### Stand-alone PV capital cost (USD/kW) for household systems under 20 W</p> <p>sa_pv_capital_cost_2 = 8780/2 ### Stand-alone PV capital cost (USD/kW) for household systems between 21-50 W</p> <p>sa_pv_capital_cost_3 = 6380/2 ### Stand-alone PV capital cost (USD/kW) for household systems between 51-100 W</p> <p>sa_pv_capital_cost_4 = 4470/2 ### Stand-alone PV capital cost (USD/kW) for household systems between 101-1000 W</p> <p>sa_pv_capital_cost_5 = 6950/2 ### Stand-alone PV capital cost (USD/kW) for household systems over 1 kW</p>
3	Higher demand for rural areas	Rural demand: 2,400 kWh/household/year Urban demand: 9,600 kWh/household/year	<p># PV and Wind hybrid mini-grid costs</p> <p>pv_cost = 1600 # PV panel costs including BoS (PV inverter, charge controller) (USD/kW)</p> <p>battery_cost = 1000 # battery capital cost, USD/kWh of storage capacity</p> <p>inverter_cost = 230 # Battery inverter, USD/kW</p> <p>diesel_gen_cost = 378 # diesel generator capital cost, USD/kW rated power</p> <p>wind_cost = 2800</p> <p>sa_pv_capital_cost_1 = 9620 ### Stand-alone PV capital cost (USD/kW) for household systems under 20 W</p> <p>sa_pv_capital_cost_2 = 8780 ### Stand-alone PV capital cost (USD/kW) for household systems between 21-50 W</p> <p>sa_pv_capital_cost_3 = 6380 ### Stand-alone PV capital cost (USD/kW) for household systems between 51-100 W</p> <p>sa_pv_capital_cost_4 = 4470 ### Stand-alone PV capital cost (USD/kW) for household systems between 101-1000 W</p> <p>sa_pv_capital_cost_5 = 6950 ### Stand-alone PV capital cost (USD/kW) for household systems over 1 kW</p>

3. Results

Results of Scenario 1 Business as usual (BAU)

The existing grid is given in figure 3 in the colour purple. Currently the electricity in the capital (Paramaribo) and the districts around the capital is provided with the existing grid. So, in 2030 this can also be the case with more new connections and grid extension. In the other districts as Nickerie and Marowijne there is also a grid and this can provide the electricity in 2030 also. For the interior, the least cost technology options till 2030 are stand alone PV, mini grid PV hybrid systems and mini grid hydro systems. At most of the settlements, stand alone PV systems can be installed.

Figure 3 Least cost technology – BAU

In the districts with existing grid the LCOE is \$0.087 to \$0.12 per kWh (Fig.4). While in the interior most of the villages where stand-alone PV system can be installed the LCOE can range from \$0.30 to \$0.40 per kWh. At some locations in the interior with mini grid PV hybrid the LCOE can be higher than \$1 per kWh. Along the Suriname river, mini grid hydro is an option with an LCOE of \$0.12 – \$0.30 per kWh.

Figure 4 LCOE – BAU

In order to have 100% electrification rate till 2030, an investment of \$292 million needs to be made of which \$215 million will be required for the existing grid (Fig. 5). Further, 52MW new capacity needs to be installed (Fig. 6). A total of 117,593 new connections will be made of which 57,818 will be to the existing grid. Furthermore, 41,038 will be stand alone PV systems, 16,085 will be mini grid hydroelectric system, 2434 will be grid extension and the remaining will be mini grid PV hybrid systems (Fig 7).

Figure 5 Investment cost 2030 – BAU

Figure 6 New connections 2030 – BAU

Figure 7 New capacity added – BAU

Results of scenario 2 Lower CAPEX for PV

This scenario is the same compared to BAU, only the CAPEX of PV for mini grids and stand alone PV systems has been 0.5 times lower compared to BAU.

Compared to BAU, it can be seen that along the Suriname river more stand alone PV systems can be installed instead of mini grid hydro because the cost will be less.

Figure 8 Least cost technology – scenario 2

In the districts with existing grid the LCOE is \$0.087 to \$0.12 per kWh. While in the interior most of the villages where stand-alone PV system can be installed, the LCOE can range from \$0.12 to \$0.20 per kWh. At some locations in the interior with mini grid PV hybrid the LCOE can be higher than \$1 per kWh. Compared to BAU, the LCOE of stand alone PV systems will be cheaper if the CAPEX is 0.5x times lower. And as the CAPEX will be less compared to BAU, more stand alone PV systems can be installed along the Suriname river instead of mini grid hydro.

Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) - Scenario 2
(Lower CAPEX of PV)

Figure 9 LCOE – Scenario 2

In order to have 100% electrification rate till 2030, an investment of \$257 million needs to be made which is \$35 million less compared to BAU. Around \$215 million will be required for the existing grid (Fig. 10). Further, 52MW new capacity needs to be installed (Fig. 12). A total of 117,593 new connections will be made of which 57,818 will be to the existing grid. Furthermore, 57,169 will be stand alone PV systems, 2,273 will be mini grid hydroelectric system, with no grid extension and the remaining will be mini grid PV hybrid systems (Fig 11).

Figure 10 Investment cost 2030 – scenario 2

Figure 11 New connections 2030 – scenario 2

Figure 12 New capacity added – scenario 2

Results of scenario 3 Higher demand for rural areas

Compared to BAU and 2, it can be seen that along the Suriname river and Marowijne river and in the districts Sipaliwini more mini grid hydro systems can be installed. If the demand goes up in the rural areas besides more mini grid hydro, also mini grid wind system can be installed near Galibi (along the Marowijne river, a settlement in the northeastern part of Suriname).

Least Cost Technolgy - Scenario 3
(Higher demand for rural areas)

Figure 13 Least cost technology – scenario 3

In the districts with existing grid the LCOE is \$0.087 to \$0.12 per kWh. While in the interior with most of the villages where mini hydro, stand-alone PV system, mini grid PV hybrid can be installed, the LCOE can range from \$0.40 to \$1.00 per kWh. At some locations in the interior with mini grid PV hybrid the LCOE can be higher than \$1 per kWh. This can be due to the accessibility of the settlements. Some villages in the interior are accessible only by a boat or a plane because there is no proper infrastructure in the interior. The LCOE of this scenario is higher for all the systems, besides LCOE of the existing grid, compared to BAU and 2.

Levelized cost of energy (LCOE) - Scenario 3
(higher demand for rural areas)

Figure 14 LCOE – Scenario 3

In order to have 100% electrification rate till 2030, an investment of \$360 million needs to be made which is \$68million more compared to BAU. Around \$217 million will be required for the existing grid (Fig. 15). Further, 61MW new capacity needs to be installed (Fig. 17). A total of 117,592 new connections will be made of which 57,818 will be to the existing grid. Furthermore, 33,926 will be stand alone PV systems, 20,240 will be mini grid hydroelectric system, with 4,708 grid extension, 734 with hybrid wind and the remaining will be mini grid PV hybrid systems (Fig 16).

Figure 15 Investment cost 2030 – scenario 3

Figure 16 New connections 2030 – scenario 3

Figure 17 New capacity added – scenario 3

5. Discussion

In order to have 100% electrification rate till 2030, there are several options as the least cost electrification option for different settlements in Suriname like the existing grid, stand alone PV systems, mini grid hydro systems, mini grid wind hybrid systems, mini grid PV hybrid systems and grid extension. The least cost electrification option is dependent on the demand of the settlement, CAPEX an OPEX of the system, the distance of the settlement to the existing infrastructure, the availability of the grid and the resources available at the settlement (e.g. GHI, hydro potential etc). Until 2023, nearly 117,593 new connections need to be made in order to reach the 100% electrification rate. The people in the urban areas can be connected to the existing grid or the grid can be extended while the people in the rural areas can be electrified by with stand alone PV systems, mini grid PV systems, mini grid hydro systems or mini grid wind hybrid. Around 50% of the new connections can be made using the existing grid. For all the 3 scenarios it is significant that the most settlements that are not connected to the grid, can be electrified with stand alone PV systems. This can be due to the small size of the population in those settlements and due to lack of proper infrastructure in those places. For the BAU, scenario 2 and 3 is that respectively 35%, 49% and 29%. For the second scenario it is higher because the CAPEX of PV was 0.5 times lower than the other 2 scenarios. Settlements connections with stand alone PV is around 200 times more than with mini grid PV systems.

For the BAU, scenario 2 and 3 the respectively percentage which can be electrified with mini hydro is 14%, 2% and 17%.

Around 52 to 61MW is required till 2030 to electrify all the settlements. Further, around \$250 to \$360 million will be required to get the electrification rate at 100% till 2030. Scenario 2 will be cheaper compared to the other scenarios so if the PV cost goes down then it will be less expensive. In scenario 1 we see the highest electricity costs in the rural areas, which are often the poorest. Perhaps if PV is subsidized, then the cost of electricity would be more equal in Suriname (although that would cost more for the government or whoever provides the subsidy). The LCOE is also lower for this scenario compared to the other scenarios. While the most expensive option is the third scenario, when the demand of the rural areas will increase. The investment will be mainly done in stand alone PV systems and mini grid hydro systems. And the LCOE will also be higher compared to the other two scenarios.

Figure 18 New connections 2030 – scenario comparison

Figure 19 New capacity 2030 – scenario comparison

Figure 20 Investment 2030 – scenario comparison

Some of the required infrastructure data could not be found in open databases, therefore estimates of the locations of existing power lines were used. In order to make this study more realistic to the situation of Suriname, instead of using proxy satellite data it would be advisable to use actual data of Suriname e.g. medium voltage lines, high voltage lines etc. This will give more insight into the current situation and will lead to better results.

7. Conclusion

In order to have 100% electrification rate for Suriname till 2030, there are several options as the least cost electrification option for different settlements in Suriname like the existing grid, stand alone PV systems, mini grid hydro systems, mini grid wind hybrid systems, mini grid PV hybrid systems and grid extension. Until 2023, nearly 117593 new connections need to be made in order to reach the 100% electrification rate. The people in the urban areas can be connected to the existing grid or the grid can be extended while the people in the rural areas can be electrified by with stand alone PV systems, mini grid PV systems, mini grid hydro systems or mini grid wind hybrid.

Around 17% new capacity will be required if the demand is higher to reach 100% electrification rate (2030). About \$290 - \$360 million new investment and 52 - 61MW of new capacity will be required to reach the electrification rate at 100% till 2030. In the interior, the investment must be mainly done in stand alone PV systems (30,000 – 40,000 new connections) and mini grid hydro systems (16,000 - 20,000 new connections).

Considering the policy side, the energy planning in the energy sector plan (ESP) must be done considering the possibilities to electrify the settlements in the interior with stand alone PV, mini grid PV hybrid and mini grid hydro hybrid systems. The Government must consider coming with incentives, investment schemes and a proper planning to encourage Distributed Renewable Energy (DRE) in Suriname, especially in the interior.

References

1. Anon., 2024. *iopscience*. [Online]
Available at: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/aa7b29/meta>
[Accessed 31 January 2024].
2. Anon., 2024. Gonini. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.gonini.org/>
[Accessed 9 January 2024]
3. Anon., 2024. diva-gis. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.diva-gis.org/gdata>
[Accessed 9 January 2024]
4. Anon., 2024. diva-gis. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.diva-gis.org/gdata>
[Accessed 9 January 2024]
5. Anon., 2024. eogdata. [Online]
Available at: https://eogdata.mines.edu/products/vnl/#annual_v2
[Accessed 9 January 2024]
6. Anon., 2024. globalsolaratlas. [Online]
Available at: <https://globalsolaratlas.info/map>
[Accessed 9 January 2024]
7. Anon., 2024. globalwindatlas. [Online]
Available at: <https://globalwindatlas.info/en>
[Accessed 9 January 2024]
8. Anon., 2024. gridfinder. [Online]
Available at: <https://gridfinder.rdrn.me/>
[Accessed 9 January 2024]
9. Anon., 2024. malariaatlas. [Online]
Available at: <https://data.malariaatlas.org/maps>
[Accessed 9 January 2024]
10. Anon., 2024. rackingsdg7. [Online]
Available at: <https://trackingsdg7.esmap.org/country/suriname>
[Accessed 9 January 2024]
11. Anon., 2024. macrotrends. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.macrotrrends.net/countries/SUR/suriname/urban-population#:~:text=Suriname%20urban%20population%20for%202022,a%201.16%25%20increase%20from%202018.>
[Accessed 9 January 2024]
12. Anon., 2024. globaldatalab. [Online]
Available at:
<https://globaldatalab.org/areadata/table/hhsize/SUR/?levels=1+4&interpolation=0&extra-polation=0>
[Accessed 9 January 2024]
13. Korkovelos, A., Khavari, B., Sahlberg, A., Howells, M. and Arderne, C., 2019. The role of open access data in geospatial electrification planning and the achievement of SDG7. an OnSSET-based case study for Malawi. *Energies*, 12(7), p.1395.

14. Sahlberg, A., Khavari, B., Mohamed, I. and Fuso Nerini, F., 2023. Comparison of Least-Cost Pathways towards Universal Electricity Access in Somalia over Different Timelines. *Energies*, 16(18), p.6489.
15. Anon., 2024. OnSSET. [Online]
Available at: <http://www.onsset.org/>
[Accessed 9 January 2024]
16. Anon., 2024. gep-onsset. [Online]
Available at: <https://gep-onsset.readthedocs.io/en/latest/GIS%20data%20collection.html>
[Accessed 9 January 2024]
17. Anon., 2024. Global Electrification Platform. [Online]
Available at: <https://electrifynow.energydata.info/>
[Accessed 9 January 2024]

Appendices

Appendix 1

Modelling period & Targets			
	Start year	2020	year
	Intermediate year	2025	year
	End year	2030	year
	Current national electricity access rate	98.8%	percentage
	- Urban elec. rate	99.5%	percentage
	- Rural elec. rate	96.0%	percentage
	Target access rate in intermediate year	100.0%	share
	Target access rate in end year	100.0%	share
Population data			
	Total population (start year)	607065	
	Urban pop ratio (start year)	0.820	
	Rural pop ratio (start year)	0.180	
	Pop growth rate	1.0%	percentage
	Total population (end year)	670,577	
	Urban pop ratio (end year)	0.8200	
	Rural pop ratio (end year)	0.1800	
	Urban Household size	3.9	people/HH
	Rural Household size	3.9	people/HH
Technology specs & costs			
Centralized Grid	Grid generating cost	0.100	USD/kWh
	Expected CAPEX of power plants	5000.00	USD/kW
	Annual Cap on New Grid Capacity	140.0	MW/year
	Annual Cap on New Grid Connections	52,000	connections/year
T&D	Transmission losses	10.0%	percentage
	Distribution losses	8.0%	percentage
	T&D Operation & Maintenance cost	3.0%	
	HV line type	66	kV
	Indicative HV line cost	180,000	USD/km
	MV line type	11 or 33	kV
	Indicative MV line cost	50,000	USD/km
	Max MV line stretch	50.00	km

	LV line type	0.24	kV
	lv_line_cost	no data	USD/km
	Max Lv line stretch	0.80	km
	HV to MV transformer cost	no data	USD/unit
	MV to LV transformet cost	15,000	USD/unit
	Service transformer type	50.00	kVa
	Service transformer cost	no data	USD/unit
	Max no of connections per service transformer	300	connections
	Service drop / connection cost	no data	USD/con
Mini grids			
Diesel generator	Diesel pump price	1.00	USD/liter
	Diesel generator cost	378	USD/kVA
	Diesel generator life	10	years
	Diesel generator O&M cost	10.0%	percentage
PV	PV module cost	1147.00	USD/kW
	PV panel life	25.00	years
	PV O&M cost	1.5%	percentage
Wind	Wind turbine cost	2800.00	USD/kW
	Wind turbine life	20.00	years
	Wind turbine O&M cost	1.5%	percentage
Hydro	Small scale hydro (indicative) cost	3000.00	USD/kW
	Small scale hydro life	30.00	years
	Small scale hydro O&M cost	1.5%	percentage
BoS (for mini grids)	Battery cost	427.00	USD/kWh
	Inverter cost	608.00	USD /kW
	Inverter life	10.00	years
	Charge/Discharge efficiency of battery	0.92	percentage
	Maximum depth of discharge of battery	0.8	percentage
	Charge controller	142	USD/unit
	Maximum loss of load	0.5%	percentage
	Service drop / connection cost	50.00	USD/con
Solar Home Systems	SHS costs classification		
	< 0.02 kW	9,620	USD/kW
	0.02-0.05 W	8,780	USD/kW
	0.05-0.1 W	6,380	USD/kW
	0.1-1 W	4,470	USD/kW
	> 1 kW	6,950	USD/kW
	SHS life	15	years
	SHS O&M	1.5%	percentage

Other			
	Discount rate	8.0%	percentage
Demand Targets			
Residential sector	Total estimated demand in 2030	573	GWh
	Target Demand for Urban settlements	103	kWh/cap/year
	Target Demand for Rural settlements	5	kWh/cap/year
Social infrastructure			
Health facilities	Total estimated demand in 2030	18.4	GWh
	Service level 1	4	kWh/day/facility
	Service level 2	40	kWh/day/facility
	Service level 3	1200	kWh/day/facility
Education facilities	Total estimated demand in 2030	1	GWh
	Primary	2.0	kWh/day/facility
	Secondary	7.7	kWh/day/facility
	Un-defined	4.5	kWh/day/facility